

TEXTILE REINFORCED CEMENT COMPOSITES FOR THE DESIGN OF VERY THIN SADDLE SHELLS: A CASE STUDY

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Abstract

The reinforcement of a specifically developed fine grained cement matrix with glass fibre textiles in high fibre volume fractions creates a composite that has -besides its usual compressive strength - an important tensile capacity. This cement composite is particularly suitable for strongly curved lightweight structures. These building applications do not only benefit from the cement composite's flexible reinforcement and high mechanical capacities, but more importantly they take advantage of the cement composite's fire safety.

This paper evaluates the application of textile reinforced cement (TRC) composites in small span shell structures. Omitting the need for steel reinforcement and thus concrete cover, TRC composite shells could be made significantly thinner, and thus lighter, than traditional steel-reinforced concrete shells. The presented research quantifies this material gain by performing the entire design of a case study: a 10 m span TRC saddle shell.

1 Introduction

The research in this paper addresses to the renewed interest for structurally curved shapes by the building design society. This interest is nurtured particularly by the attractive properties of fibre reinforced composites, facilitating the fabrication of strongly curved shapes. The fire resistance and cost of polymer matrix composites can however hamper their use in building applications.

Fibre reinforced cement matrix composites are a fire safe alternative for fibre reinforced polymers, but are limited in fibre volume fraction when short fibres are used in a premix system, as is usually the case. Researchers at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel developed a fine grained cement matrix - Inorganic

Phosphate Cement (IPC) [1]- which can impregnate dense glass fibre textiles and achieve herewith fibre volume fractions of more than 20 % [2][3]. As the IPC matrix becomes pH-neutral after hardening, cheap E-glass fibres can moreover be used instead of the more expensive AR-glass fibres necessary for ordinary Portland cement based composites. Glass fibre Textile Reinforced Inorganic Phosphate Cement (GTR-IPC) consequently has a high and durable tensile as well as compressive capacity and presents an interesting and fire safe composite for highly curved building applications with a structural function.

This paper studies the application of high fibre volume fraction Textile Reinforced Cement (TRC) composites such as GTR-IPC in thin, highly curved, small span (<15 m) roof shells. The application of textile reinforced cement composites in shells has two main advantages over the traditionally used steel-reinforced concrete. First, the use of flexible fibre textile reinforcement eliminates the labour intensive and thus costly process of shaping and placing the steel reinforcement. Secondly, using high fibre volume fractions of non-corroding glass fibre reinforcement, the steel reinforcement and the concrete cover necessary to avoid its corrosion, can be eliminated. Taking into account the practically unlimited minimum thickness of the composite (minimum laminate thickness equals 1 mm), textile reinforced cement composite shells can be designed only as thick as structurally necessary. This property becomes particularly advantageous for shells with smaller spans (< 15 m) [4].

This paper addresses the question how much thinner a small span shell can be made in high fibre volume fraction TRC composites, and thus what material and weight gain can be established, with reference to a steel-reinforced concrete shell. Therefore, a case study implying the analysis and design of a 10 m

span saddle shell in GTR-IPC is performed. This design first of all involves the generation of a force-efficient shell surface geometry. The optimal shape under self-weight loading is obtained by form finding using the dynamic relaxation method [5][6]. Then, the shell is structurally analysed and designed, determining its minimum thickness (including locally thickened areas) to limit deformations, resist stresses and avoid buckling under all critical load combinations of self weight, wind, snow and service point load based on Eurocode prescriptions. Therefore, a full material and geometrical nonlinear analysis is performed using Abaqus finite element (FE) software. Prior to the description of the shell design, this paper presents the mechanical behaviour of GTR-IPC, the applied safety factors and resulting design strength values, and the finite element material modelling of its highly nonlinear constitutive behaviour.

2 Glass fibre Textile Reinforced Inorganic Phosphate Cement (GTR-IPC)

2.1 Material behaviour

For its application in shells, in which principal stress directions vary over the shell surface as well as under various load combinations, the Inorganic Phosphate Cement is reinforced with randomly oriented, chopped glass fibre (50 mm length) mats up to about 20 % fibre volume fraction. Due to the dense and homogeneous distribution of the low-diameter fibres in the matrix throughout the shell surface and section, GTR-IPC can be assumed homogeneous and isotropic within a very small scale (approximately 1 cm) [7].

GTR-IPC possesses a strong asymmetry in tensile and compressive behaviour. While this composite can be assumed to behave linearly elastic in compression (Young modulus equals 18 GPa) [8], matrix crack initiation and propagation provokes a nonlinear behaviour and stiffness decrease in tension. The addition of a high fibre volume fraction (20 % or more) to the brittle matrix assures a considerably high tensile stiffness and strength in the post-cracking stage (see Figure 1). Hence, the cement composite can be applied in both tensile and compressive loadbearing applications such as anticlastic shells.

Fig.1. Experimental tensile stress-strain behaviour of GTR-IPC for increasing fibre volume % [2]

2.2 Constitutive finite element modelling

The cement composite's post-cracking tensile capacity can only be used in structural applications if modelled accordingly, namely with a constitutive behaviour which is different in tension and compression, and nonlinear in tension. This behaviour is modelled in FE program Abaqus with the concrete Smeared crack model [9].

The concrete Smeared crack model consists of two independent 'failure' surfaces in tension and compression. While the yield criterion determines if a point becomes plastic in compression (unimportant for GTR-IPC modelling as the composite is assumed to be linearly elastic up to the compressive design strength), an independent crack detection surface determines if a point 'fails' by cracking.

After crack detection, the Smeared crack model properly simulates the nonlinear tension stiffening of GTR-IPC by introduction of the material's post-cracking stress-strain relation. The concrete model is a Smeared crack model in the sense that it does not track individual cracks. Constitutive calculations are performed independently at each integration point, and the presence of cracks enters into these calculations by affecting the stress and material stiffness associated with the integration point.

2.3 Design strength values

20 fibre volume % GTR-IPC has an average uniaxial compressive strength of 80 MPa [8] and an average uniaxial tensile strength of 50 MPa [2]. To take into account the negative influence of biaxial tensile-tensile stress states occurring in the shell, the composite's tensile strength is reduced with 20 % [10]. On top of this, a partial material safety factor

should be applied onto the characteristic strength. Due to the limited amount of strength data, and thus the inability to determine a statistically meaningful characteristic strength, the abovementioned average values are used in combination with an increased safety factor of 2 (instead of safety factor of 1.5 as prescribed in concrete [11]). Table 1 sets out GTR-IPC's resulting design strength values as well as other general properties.

Density	ρ	kg/m ³	1900
Young modulus (in compression)	E_c	GPa	18
Poisson coefficient	ν		0.3
Design tensile strength	$\sigma_{t,d}$	MPa	20
Design compressive strength	$\sigma_{c,d}$	MPa	40

Table 1: Material properties of GTR-IPC

In the design of GTR-IPC shells, the composite's durability and fatigue behaviour should also be taken into account. Recent durability studies by Remy et al. [12] on 11% and 23% volume fraction GTR-IPC showed that cyclic environmental loading (freezing-thawing and wetting-drying) has no negative influence on the composite's tensile strength. On the level of stiffness degradation, freezing-thawing also had no effect, while 60 wetting-drying cycles only decreased the initial tensile stiffness with about 20 % but not the global tensile stiffness.

Fatigue tests (one million tensile loading cycles) on the 23 % random GTR-IPC were also performed: loading up to 22 MPa did not cause failure, but loading up to 30 MPa did cause failure of the specimens for less than one million cycles [12]. The design tensile strength value of 20 MPa (see Table 1) is thus a safe assumption concerning fatigue failure. The cyclic loading tests did however decrease the linearised cycle tensile stiffness with maximally 20%, a global stiffness reduction which must be taken into account in the shell design (i.e. in deflection limit verification in serviceability limit state; the effect on ultimate limit state strength and buckling verification is assumed to be governed by the high safety factors applied onto the structure's resistance).

3 Shell modelling and calculation hypotheses

3.1 10 m span saddle shell: geometry

The conceptual design of the case study is a saddle shaped shell covering a square area of 10 m by 10 m. The vertical arch edges span 10 m with a maximum height of 5 m. The midspan height of the final surface is a priori set to 2.85 m to ensure sufficient clearance for people underneath the shell.

In order to obtain an anticlastic shell surface which fulfils the abovementioned geometrical criteria while showing the optimal stress state of pure membrane action (both tension and compression) under the shell's own weight, the shell surface – hanging between temporarily fixed arch edges – is form found using the dynamic relaxation method with kinetic damping. An elaborate discussion of this process can be found in [13]. Figure 2 shows the resulting shell shape, optimal under its own weight.

Fig.2. Geometry of saddle shell case study with indication of locally thickened areas (yellow)

Based on previous research [14], an initial global shell thickness of 20 mm is attributed to the shell. The shell is moreover locally thickened at the bottom half of the arch edges (over a height of 3 m) to increase the shell's stiffness against lateral wind loads.

3.2 Shell finite element modelling

The anticlastic GTR-IPC shell is modelled in the FE program Abaqus (version 6.7-1). The shell is globally meshed with 40x40 (approximate element size of 0.25 m) 4-node doubly curved shell elements (S4R) to ensure computational convergence (see Figure 3). To study the stresses locally provoked by the point load, the load is realistically represented by a distributed load over a square area of 0.2 x 0.2 m, and the mesh was locally refined up to 0.05 m approximate element size. The two side edges in

contact with the ground are pinned along their whole length (Figure 3).

Fig.3. Finite element model of form found saddle shell

3.3 Load cases and design limits

On top of the permanent selfweight load, the considered variable load cases are wind, snow and service point load. The quasi-static wind load case is determined on the shell canopy. The quasi-static approach is valid, as the final shell design has a first eigenfrequency ($f_1 = 5.6$ Hz) exceeding 5 Hz. The vertical service point load (1.5 kN) must not be considered in combination with other variable loads. It is placed at discrete locations where its effect is expected to be the largest: in the middle of the shell, in the middle of one of the arch edges, and at one quarter of the arch length.

According to the Eurocode [15], two limit states must be verified: the serviceability (SLS) and ultimate limit state (ULS). The SLS criterion involves that deformations must remain below $\text{span}/250$ under the characteristic load combination of all abovementioned loads. For ULS verification, the strength of the shell (maximum stresses must remain below design strength values, see Table 1) and buckling resistance (including safety factor) is evaluated under the fundamental load combination (including safety factor of 1.35 on selfweight, and 1.5 on variable loads).

In order to evaluate the stability of the shell structure, a nonlinear, large-deflection, static analysis considering material and geometrical nonlinearity is performed. The effects of eventual geometrical imperfections are taken into account by application of a reduction factor onto the buckling load of 0.7 [16]. Moreover a partial safety factor onto the buckling resistance of 3.5 is applied, corresponding to the most conservative IASS (International Association of Shell and Spatial

Structures) design recommendations for buckling of concrete shells [17].

4 Analysis and design of a 10 m span saddle shell case study

The iterative linear analysis of the saddle shell with varying thicknesses under all load combinations of selfweight, wind, snow, and service point load, and with reference to the limit state criteria, determined following preliminary design: a global minimum shell thickness of 15 mm and local thickenings of 50 mm. This shell design is now verified by a full material and geometrical nonlinear analysis.

4.1 SLS: Shell deformations

The largest displacements occur under the SLS load combination of selfweight, wind and snow, however deformations remain relatively low. The maximum global displacement of the shell equals 7.0 mm, which is still more than five times lower than the SLS limit ($\text{span}/250 = 10 \text{ m}/250 = 40 \text{ mm}$). These small displacements show the high global stiffness of the double curved shell.

Due to the large margin between calculated displacements and displacement limit, an eventual stiffness decrease of 20 % due to environmental or mechanical repeated loading will not be problematic for the serviceability of the structure.

4.2 ULS: Material strength and shell stability

For verification of the ULS of strength, the combination of selfweight and point load at the centre of one of the arch edges is the dominating load combination. For the globally 15 mm thick shell with 50 mm local thickenings, maximum stresses remain largely below the design limits: in tension $\sigma_{t,\max} = 6.6 \text{ MPa} < \sigma_{t,d} = 20 \text{ MPa}$ and in compression $\sigma_{c,\max} = 15.4 \text{ MPa} < \sigma_{c,d} = 40 \text{ MPa}$.

The ULS of stability is verified by performing a material and geometrical nonlinear analysis of the shell submitted to a gradually increasing load, namely the point load ($1.5\text{kN} \cdot 1.5$ load safety factor) at the centre of the arch edge, scaled with a load factor, and superposed to the shell's own weight. Deformations (global and vertical) and maximum tensile and compressive stresses are tracked under this increasing load (see Table 2). The results show that for 3.5 times the service point load (load factor = 3.5), the maximum occurring compressive stress

exceeds GTR-IPC's nominal compressive strength (80 MPa), while the shell's deformations are still continuously increasing; no instability or outrageous deflections are observed. The displacements under a load factor of 3.5 even remain below the SLS limit ($35 \text{ mm} < \text{span}/250 = 40 \text{ mm}$). Hence, not buckling but material failure will govern, and the compression material safety factor of 2 must be handled. Showing still no instability for an applied load factor of 3.5, the shell design thus fulfils the ULS of buckling.

Load factor	U_{\max} (mm)	$U_{3,\max}$ (mm)	$\sigma_{t,\max}$ (MPa)	$\sigma_{c,\max}$ (MPa)
1	5.2	3.9	6.6	-15.4
2	11.9	8.9	11.4	-35.5
2.5	16.3	12.3	14.6	-48.5
3	22.5	17.0	19.2	-65.7
3.25	27	20.4	22.9	-77.4
3.5	34.6	26.3	29.5	< -80

Table 2: Evolution of maximum stresses and displacements in 15 mm thick, locally 50 mm thickened, GTR-IPC shell under increasing point load, nonlinear analysis

5 GTR-IPC saddle shell: evaluation of final design

The previous full nonlinear analysis and design of the anticlastic GTR-IPC shell spanning an area of 10 m x 10 m showed that a global shell thickness of 15 mm combined with a local thickness increase of 50 mm at the bottom of the arch edges (over about 1 m width and less than 3 m height) suffices to fulfil all SLS and ULS limit states. Using GTR-IPC as a material in anticlastic shells, force-efficient small span shells can thus be designed that achieve a thickness to span ratio (1/666) of the same order of magnitude as Heinz Isler's most slender large span shells [18].

Steel-reinforced concrete shells could however never achieve such slenderness for small spans because of the concrete cover necessary to avoid corrosion of the steel reinforcement. Following current European concrete standards (Eurocode 2 [11]), the minimum thickness of a concrete element exposed to weathering conditions at both sides equals about 70 mm. Considering this minimum thickness for steel-reinforced concrete shells, the case study shows that

the application of high fibre volume fraction TRC composites such as GTR-IPC for small span shells can reduce the thickness and thus the amount of material used with a factor of about 4.5 ($70/15 = 4.7$). Or, alternatively, the thickness and amount of material used for the GTR-IPC shell is only about 20 % of that of a steel-reinforced concrete shell. On the level of weight gain, assuming an average steel-reinforced concrete density of 2500 kg/m^3 , the 10 m span GTR-IPC shell weighs about 30 kg/m^2 and thus 6 times less than a traditional steel-reinforced concrete shell (175 kg/m^2) with the same span.

The application of GTR-IPC in small span shells is not only a durable concept from the shell material use point of view, but its reduced weight also allows significant reductions in cost and CO_2 - emissions of foundations, transportation and construction.

6 Conclusions

This paper studies the application of high fibre volume fraction TRC composites, such as GTR-IPC, to design very thin small span ($< 15 \text{ m}$) shells. In this objective, an exemplary 10 m span saddle shell in GTR-IPC is designed, starting from the determination of an optimal geometry and going to the full nonlinear analysis of the shell.

The structural design integrates all current knowledge on the cement composite's behaviour, namely its nonlinear tensile behaviour and finite element modelling, as well as its durability behaviour integrated in the definition of design strength values. The loads and limit states to consider are based on current European standards (Eurocode).

The design of the 10 m span case study determined the minimum global shell thickness to be only 15 mm, with only very local thickenings of 50 mm. Conclusively, taking advantage of the exclusive mechanical properties of high fibre volume fraction textile reinforced cement composites such as GTR-IPC, renewing very thin shell structures can be designed, unseen for steel-reinforced concrete shells for such small spans. The case study is a convincing illustration of the great potential of strongly textile reinforced cement composites in small span shells and, more generally, in highly curved elements with a structural function.

References

- [1] EP 0 861 216 B1. Inorganic Resin Compositions, Their Preparation And Use Thereof.
- [2] Remy, O. and Wastiels, J. (2008). High performance textile reinforced cements: tensile hardening behaviour and modelling. Proceedings of the International Conference on Challenges for Civil Construction (CCC), A. Marques, L. Juvandes, A. Henriques, R. Faria, J. Barros, A. Ferreira, editors, 116-117 and cd-rom.
- [3] Remy, O. and Wastiels, J. (2010). Development of Impregnation Technique for Glass Fibre Mats to Process Textile Reinforced Cementitious Composites. *Plastics, Rubbers and Composites*, 39(3/4/5), 195-199.
- [4] Tysmans, T., Adriaenssens, S., Cuypers, H. and Wastiels, J. (2009). Structural analysis of small span textile reinforced concrete shells with double curvature. *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 69, No. 11-12, pp 1790-1796.
- [5] Barnes, M.R. (1999). Form-finding and analysis of tension structures by dynamic relaxation. *International Journal of Space Structures*, 14(2), 89-104.
- [6] Adriaenssens S.M.L. and Barnes M.R. (2001). Tensegrity spline beam and grid shell structures. *Engineering Structures*, 23(1), 29-36.
- [7] Cuypers, H. and Wastiels, J. (2008). Thin and Strong Concrete Composites with Glass Textile Reinforcement: Modeling the Tensile Response. Proceedings SP-250 Textile Reinforced Concrete, A. Dubey, editor, cd-rom paper ID: SP-250-10, 131-148.
- [8] Cuypers, H. (2002). Analysis and design of Sandwich Panels with Brittle Matrix Composite Faces for Building Applications. Doctoral Thesis, Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Faculty of Engineering Sciences, 235 pages.
- [9] Abaqus 6.7-1 Documentation a. Abaqus Analysis User's Manual - Part V: Materials, Chapter 18: Inelastic Mechanical Properties, Section 18.5.1: Concrete - Concrete smeared cracking.
- [10] Tysmans, T. (2010). Design of anticlastic shells in innovative textile reinforced cement composites. Doctoral Thesis, Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Faculty of Engineering Sciences, 270 pages.
- [11] European Committee for Standardisation (2004). Eurocode 2: Design of concrete structures. CEN.
- [12] Wastiels, J., Remy, O. (2011). Industrial processing technique for textile reinforced cement composites with structural use. Proceedings HPFRCC6, Ann-Harbor, Michigan, accepted for publication
- [13] Tysmans, T., Adriaenssens, S. and Wastiels, J. Form finding methodology for force-modelled anticlastic shells in glass fibre textile reinforced cement composites. *Engineering Structures*, accepted for publication.
- [14] Tysmans, T., Adriaenssens, S. and Wastiels, J. (2009). Shape optimization of small span textile reinforced cementitious composite shells. Proceedings (p 408-109) and on cd-rom of IASS 2009 Symposium: Evolution and trends in design, analysis and construction of shell and spatial structures, 28 September – 2 October 2009, Valencia, 1755-1766.
- [15] European Committee for Standardisation (2002a). Eurocode - Basis of structural design. CEN.
- [16] Dulácska, E. and Kollár, L. (1995). Design Procedure for the Buckling Analysis of Reinforced Concrete Shells. *Thin-Walled Structures*, 23(1-4), 313-321.
- [17] Medwadowski, S.J. (2004). Buckling of concrete shells: an overview. *Journal of the International Association for Shell and spatial Structures*, 45(1), 51-63.
- [18] Chilton, J. (2000). *The Engineer's Contribution to Contemporary Architecture - Heinz Isler*. Thomas Telford Publishing, London, UK, 170 pages.